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Master's Thesis

Multiphase AC Optimal Power Flow Analysis

written by

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Abstract

Solving optimal power flow using linearization of non-convex functions has various applications in optimizing the operation and design of power systems. Existing algorithms which utilize linearization technique for solving OPF do not take existence of power flow solution. This thesis proposes an algorithm which uses iterative linearization technique to optimize power system operation while keeping the condition for “existence of power flow solution” satisfied. This condition helps to keep the optimized operating point within “numerically convergent” region of power flow equations. Moreover, it also helps to automatically adjust the step size in each iteration. The proposed algorithm is used to maximize the integration of low-cost renewable energy. Since excessive renewable energy leads to decrease in its cost of generation, the optimization problem is modelled as a cost minimization problem. The proposed algorithm is modelled as a convex optimization problem by linearizing non-convex power flow equations. Moreover, essential operating limits and the condition for “existence of power flow solution” are added as constraints.

The proposed algorithm is used for optimizing the cost of operation of balanced and unbalanced multiphase power grid. Small 3 bus balanced power system is developed so that the optimization process can be visualized on the power flow manifold. It is shown that the proposed algorithm helps to automatically adjust the step size of the control variables depending on the type of grid. Different scenarios are created by varying the line impedance for each case and its behaviour is observed on power flow manifolds. For optimizing multiphase grid operation, IEEE 4 bus multiphase grid model is used. This system is extended to 6 bus power system so that more generators and loads can be included. Encouraging results were also obtained in multiphase case study.

Nomenclature

Variables

\mathbf{P}_{gen}	Vector of real power generations at all buses
P_{i-gen}	Real power generation at ith bus
\mathbf{Q}_{gen}	Vector of reactive power generations at all buses
Q_{i-gen}	Reactive power generation at ith bus
S_{i-gen}	$P_{i-gen} + Q_{i-gen}$
\mathbf{S}_{LF}	Vector of magnitude of complex power flow through each line
\mathbf{P}_{LF}	Vector of all real power flow through each line
\mathbf{u}_L	Vector of complex voltages at each pq bus
\mathbf{i}_L	Vector of complex currents at each pq bus
\mathbf{v}_L	Vector of magnitude of \mathbf{u}_L
v_i	Voltage magnitude at ith bus
\mathbf{s}_L	Vector of complex power injections at each pq bus
\mathbf{p}_L	Vector of real power injections at each pq bus
\mathbf{q}_L	Vector of reactive power injections at each pq bus
s_0	Complex power injections at slack bus
p_0	Real power injections at slack bus
q_0	Reactive power injections at slack bus
n	Total number of PQ buses
Nu	Decision variable to adjust step size in the Trust Region Algorithm

Constants

\mathbf{c}	Vector of linear coefficient of cost of real power generations at all buses
\mathbf{d}	Vector of linear coefficient of cost of reactive power generations at all buses
\mathbf{w}	Vector of no load complex voltages at each non slack bus
$(.)^{\min}$	Minimum allowed value of (.)
$(.)^{\max}$	Maximum allowed value of (.)
n	Total number of pq buses
\mathbf{Y}	Admittance matrix =

$$\begin{bmatrix} Y_{00} & \mathbf{Y}_{0L} \\ \mathbf{Y}_{L0} & \mathbf{Y}_{LL} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{(n+1) \times (n+1)}$$

$\mathbf{Y}_{00} \in \mathbb{C}^{(1) \times (1)}$ is the first element of admittance matrix and represents mutual admittance of slack bus

$\mathbf{Y}_{0L} \in \mathbb{C}^{(1) \times (n)}$ is part of admittance matrix representing connections between slack bus to non-slack buses

$\mathbf{Y}_{L0} \in \mathbb{C}^{(n) \times (1)}$ is part of admittance matrix representing connection between non-slack buses to slack bus

$\mathbf{Y}_{LL} \in \mathbb{C}^{(n) \times (n)}$ is part of admittance matrix representing connections between non-slack buses

N
$$\begin{bmatrix} I_{n \times n} & 0_{n \times n} \\ 0_{n \times n} & -I_{n \times n} \end{bmatrix}$$
 where I is identity matrix

$\widehat{(\cdot)}$ Current operating point of (\cdot)

Mathematical Operators

$\overline{(\cdot)}$ Complex Conjugate of (\cdot)

$|(\cdot)|$ Magnitude of (\cdot)

$\langle (\cdot) \rangle$
$$\begin{bmatrix} Re(\cdot) & -Img(\cdot) \\ Img(\cdot) & Re(\cdot) \end{bmatrix}$$

Acronyms

- p.u.* Per Unit
- OPF Optimal Power Flow
- LP Linear Programming
- conj complex conjugate of a matrix
- DIC Difference in Cost of Generation
- TV Tolerance value
- w.r.t With respect to
- MCICV Maximum of Change in control variables

Chapter. 1

Introduction And Motivation

1.1 Overview

Smart grid technologies have sought great attention in recent years. With increased global warming concerns and integration of renewable energy resources, the optimal utilization of energy has got more importance. Although it is still unclear what future grids will be like, it is prominent that these grids will have some common features and control strategies. One of the common operating features all future grids will seek is the optimal utilization of available energy resources. Some of the intended feature of future smart grids are:

- **Reliability** — Widespread blackouts seems to be a major challenge for future smart grids. The reason behind this is the lack of spinning reserves during high penetration of renewable energy supply. Smart grids are predicted to address this challenge and will reduce the probability of widespread blackouts.
- **Economics** — The smart grids will have the aim to maximize the utilization of excessive renewable energy resources. This excessive energy will have a cheap cost. Rescheduling of loads and generations will be done to consume the low-cost energy. This will reduce the cost of energy as well as maximize the renewable energy consumption.
- **Efficiency** — One of the important concerns in power grids are the losses. Majority of the losses are incurred in power lines while delivering power across the network. Reducing losses in an electric system also lead to less thermal stress on the system and increases the lifespan of the system.
- **Environment** — The increase in global warming is a major reason for shifting power generation to renewable energy resources. Future smart grids will always prioritize renewable energy over conventional energy resources and will try to reduce the carbon footprints.
- **Security** — The future smart grids will be more robust and are predicted to be resilient to natural disasters as well as cyber attacks.

(a) Figure shows that when renewable power generation is less, the power in grid is obtained from conventional energy resources

(b) Figure shows that when renewable power generation is high, the operating point is shifted to more power generation from renewable resources

Figure 1.1: Figure shows the change in operating point of a power grid

1.2 Motivation

Different grids have different priorities depending on the location and type of grids. For example, a grid which is located in hot climate region like gulf countries, will be more concerned about the heat generated in power distribution lines than the one in a cold climate like Iceland. Moreover, the objectives can vary from optimizing losses in power systems to optimizing the cost of generation.

Recently, with the integration of renewable energy and improvement in electric vehicle (EV) technology, the question of integrating electric vehicle into grid gained more importance. One of the main objectives in the smart grid will be to utilize maximum renewable energy to charge EVs. In such a scenario we must shift the generation from conventional energy resources to renewable resources whenever we have an excess of renewable generation. Excess of renewable energy leads to a decrease in its prices. EVs and other loads on grids can easily be modelled as fixed PQ [1] type loads. In this report, the goal is to draft out an algorithm which will maximize the integration of cheap renewable energy by shifting generations from conventional resources to renewable resources. The idea is depicted in figure 1.1.

1.3 Approach

The problem mentioned above is modelled as cost optimization problem for electric power grid operation. In mathematical terms, any optimization problem pertaining to power system operations is termed as OPF problem. The essence of OPF is to find the most suitable power system operating point while keeping certain constraints satisfied.

In an electrical power system, these constraints usually include upper and lower voltage limits on each bus, upper limits on power flow through each line and maximum generation limit of each generator. These types of constraints are modelled as inequality constraints. All these inequality constraints are related to each other using power flow equations. Power flow equations are then modelled as an equality constraint. The power flow equations are non-linear and non-convex. Dealing with power flow equations and similar equality constraints is the most challenging task while solving OPF problem.

Different approaches are used to solve OPF problem depending on the type of objective function and constraints. Some of the common methods [2] are Lambda iteration method, Gradient method, Newton method, Linear Programming (LP) method and interior point method. One of the standard online OPF programs is based on the "Lambda iteration method". This method shows fast convergence but fails to model all type of constraints accurately. "Gradient method" has slow convergence rate and faces difficulty with inequality constraints. Newton method is fast but also gives the problem with inequality constraints. Linear programming (LP) method is one of the developed methods. It handles nonlinear constraints by linearizing them. Interior point method is also the highly developed method and easily handles all type of constraints.

This report proposes an iterative convex programming method for solving OPF problem. It uses LP based technique and linearizes all nonconvex constraints especially the power flow equations. Step size is then adjusted using "existence and uniqueness" condition for power flow solution. This nonlinear but convex condition will directly be used as a convex constraint. The evolution of optimization results on power flow manifold will show how "existence and uniqueness" constraint automatically adjust the step size depending on the type of grid to be optimized. The above-mentioned procedure will be used for solving balanced and multiphase unbalanced power system problem.

Yalmip - A tool for modelling optimization problem [3]

Huge number of applications of semidefinite programming have given rise to extended research in developing software for solving the optimization problem. Number of different solvers are available online and easily downloadable to solve such problems. But modelling the optimization problems is an intensive task in such solvers and a small mistake may result in totally unacceptable results. This complexity in modelling gives rise to a need to develop a better interface and modelling language to integrate various solvers with mathematical tools like MATLAB. YALMIP was developed as a tool for matlab to model semidefinite programming problems and solve them using external solvers. This tool make development of optimization problems extremely simple. Most of the problem modelling requires very few commands to model the whole problem. YALMIP, which was originally developed to solve semidefinite problems, has evolved over time and can now handle variety of different type of problems. These includes linear programming , quadratic programming, second order cone programming (SOCP), semidefinite programming, mixed integer programming and determinant maximization etc. To solve these problems, there are tens of different solvers available online. One of the prominent feature of YALMIP is that it automatically do the analysis of the problem and then selects the

most suitable solver. If it cannot find a suitable solver installed on the computer, then it tries to convert the problem into a simpler form and then tries to solve the problem.

The OPF problem to minimize the cost of operation is modelled in MATLAB using YALMIP . GUROBI [4] is used as a solver for solving the OPF problem.

1.4 Optimal Power flow - Problem formulation

In this section, the general optimization problem will be introduced. Later on, one of the successful know methods in the area of optimal power flow is introduced. This method is commonly known as Linear programming which is based on iterative linearization technique. Afterwards, optimal power flow (OPF) problem will be formulated.

1.4.1 General Optimization Problem

A simplified version of generic optimization problem can be written as:

The optimization problem can be of minimization or of maximization type. All maximization problems can easily be written as minimization problems. Therefore, in all future discussions, it will be assumed that our optimization problem is a minimization problem.

1.4.2 Iterative Linearization technique

There are various methods of optimizing a function. Iterative linearization method is used here. This technique generally follows the following steps:

- All non-convex functions (objective and constraint functions) are linearized at the given operating point.
- A step of an appropriate length is taken in the linearized direction and a new point on the linearized manifold is obtained.

- Actual value of objective function is calculated at this new point.
- All constraints are checked at this new point (Since the minimization was done by using linearized approximation of the original non-convex functions).
- If any constraint is not breached. Then this whole procedure is repeated until converging criteria is met.
- If any constraint is breached, then the new point is rejected and above procedure is repeated with a decreased step size.

Since power flow equations are non-convex, so by using this technique, we can only find “Local minimum” [5]. Finding the global minimum is not a trivial task. Even commercially available programs use certain assumptions to find the global minima. These assumptions are often not satisfied for an usual small size power distribution system.

The two main questions which arise while using this technique for optimization are:

1. Which direction should be chosen while minimizing or maximizing a function?
2. What should be the step length in that direction?

The answer to the first question is fairly simple. It is “the opposite of gradient” and is also known as steepest descent direction.

The answer to the second question is a bit complex and highly problem specific. The step length mostly depends on objective function and constraints. The answer to this question will be provided once we will formulate the optimal power flow problem.

1.4.3 Optimal Power Flow

Optimal power flow calculation can be described as “finding the best solution for the power system operation under given specified conditions”.

Here, the best solution refers to the solution of objective function. The objective function describes our goal. It can be a minimization or maximization problem. Our goal can be minimizing losses, minimizing cost, minimizing storage utilization or maximizing renewable energy utilization etc.

The specified conditions refer to the constraints. In OPF, the compulsory constraints are power flow equations, limits on voltage magnitudes, limits on line flows and limits on each generator’s maximum real and reactive powers.

The most complicated constraint in OPF are the power flow equations. This is due to non-convexity of power flow equations. Due to complicated nature of the OPF problem, this area has been active in research for several decades.

In our optimization problem, we will choose a linear and continuous objective function for simplicity, so that we can focus more on the complexity of power flow equations. We will use linear cost function as our objective function.

Problem formulation

OPF problem is formulated as shown below:

In this problem, equation 1.1a is the objective function, which will be minimized. Equation 1.1b is the most important constraint (in any OPF problem) since it relates all inequality constraints and is non-convex. This non convex constraint will be linearized before solving the optimization problem. Equation 1.1c to 1.1e are box constraint which are already convex and linear in nature.

Methodology

In the proposed algorithm, above problem is iteratively solved until certain stopping criteria (e.g. tolerance in change of control variables or change in objective function) is achieved. As essential non-convex power flow equations are linearized, we cannot trust linearized functions far away from its linearization point. This gives rise to need of finding maximum allowable limits for movement in control variables. In [6], the writer manually set the value of maximum allowable limit for changes in control variable. This manually set value is then adjusted in up coming iterations depending on the results of previous iterations. But manually setting this maximum limit is a hit and trial method which can may give good or worst outcomes.

A novel approach is used in the proposed algorithm for finding value of maximum allowed change in control variables. For this purpose, a new constraint is added which is the condition for "existence of power flow solution". This constraint automatically limits the movement of variables within numerical stable region of the power flow manifold. This movement can be further restricted and step size can be decreased depending on the results of previous iterations. Using this technique, the goal for adjusting the step size in each iteration is achieved.

1.5 MATPOWER - A tool for balanced power system analysis [7]

Matpower is an open source tool for solving variety of power system problems. It is designed to work with Matlab and Octave. The power system problems which can

be solved using MATPOWER includes steady state power system analysis, optimization problems such as power flow (OPF), continuation power flow, unit commitment (UC) and stochastic and secure multi-interval OPF/UC. The OPF feature of MATPOWER is designed to be expandable, giving the users ability to use the optimization part according to user defined constraints, variable and cost functions. Moreover, it gives global minimum of cost minimization problem. Due to this feature, its results can serve as bench mark while developing Linear Programming based algorithms for balanced power network. One of the limitation of MATPOWER is that it handles multiphase power system by assuming it to be balanced in nature. Assuming distribution grid as balanced power system doesn't give accurate results. This give rise to a need for optimization programs which can handle unbalance multiphase systems. In this report, MATPOWER will be used to check the performance of algorithms which are developed for balanced power system. After comparison, same algorithms will be extended to multiphase power system test case.

Chapter. 2

Balanced Power System

This chapter will introduce the power system model which will be used in upcoming chapters as a base case for doing further analysis. In the first section of this chapter, a small example of 3 bus power system is presented. This example will be used in the second section to formulate the load flow problem. The third section of this chapter will introduce the fixed point method for the solution of the load flow problem. Moreover, sufficient conditions for existence and uniqueness of the solution will also be provided in the third section.

2.1 Power System Model

Consider figure 2.1 which shows 3 bus power network developed using pi model of a transmission line.

Figure 2.1: 3 Bus Power System

where:

- Y_{ft} : Admittance connected between buses "f" and "t"
- $Y_{sh,ft}$: Shunt Admittance connected between buses "f" and "t"
- i_{ft} : Current flowing from "f" to "t"
- S_i : Power injected at ith Bus
- u_i : Voltage at ith Bus

The equations for current flow can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} i_{01} &= Y_{sh,01}u_0 + Y_{01}(u_0 - u_1) & ; & & i_{10} &= Y_{sh,01}u_1 + Y_{01}(u_1 - u_0) \\ i_{12} &= Y_{sh,12}u_1 + Y_{12}(u_1 - u_2) & ; & & i_{21} &= Y_{sh,12}u_2 + Y_{12}(u_2 - u_1) \end{aligned}$$

The equation for current injected at each bus can be written as:

$$i_0 = i_{01} \quad ; \quad i_1 = i_{10} + i_{12} \quad ; \quad i_2 = i_{21}$$

$$\mathbf{i} = \begin{bmatrix} i_0 \\ i_1 \\ i_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{sh,01} + Y_{01} & -Y_{01} & 0 \\ -Y_{01} & Y_{sh,01} + Y_{01} + Y_{sh,12} + Y_{12} & -Y_{12} \\ 0 & -Y_{12} & Y_{sh,12} + Y_{12} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_0 \\ u_1 \\ u_2 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{u} \quad (2.1)$$

Power injections at each bus can be written as:

$$\mathbf{s} = \begin{bmatrix} s_0 \\ s_1 \\ s_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_0 & & \\ & u_1 & \\ & & u_2 \end{bmatrix} \text{conj} \begin{bmatrix} i_0 \\ i_1 \\ i_2 \end{bmatrix} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{u})\bar{\mathbf{i}} \quad (2.2)$$

2.2 Formulation of Load flow Problem

Suppose bus '0' is the slack bus and all other 'n' buses are PQ buses. Then we can re-write equation 2.1 and 2.2 by separating power at slack and pq buses as:

$$\mathbf{s} = \begin{bmatrix} s_0 \\ \mathbf{s}_L \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_0 & \\ & \mathbf{u}_L \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{i}_0 \\ \bar{\mathbf{i}}_L \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{i} = \begin{bmatrix} i_0 \\ \mathbf{i}_L \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{00} & \mathbf{Y}_{0L} \\ \mathbf{Y}_{L0} & \mathbf{Y}_{LL} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_0 \\ \mathbf{u}_L \end{bmatrix}$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y}_{00} &\in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times 1} & ; & & \mathbf{Y}_{\neq L} &\in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times n} \\ \mathbf{Y}_{L0} &\in \mathbb{C}^{n \times 1} & ; & & \mathbf{Y}_{LL} &\in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n} \end{aligned}$$

Now we can write the equation for 'n' pq buses using above equations as:

$$\mathbf{s}_L = \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_L)\bar{\mathbf{i}}_L \quad (2.3a)$$

$$\mathbf{i}_L = \mathbf{Y}_{L0}u_0 + \mathbf{Y}_{LL}\mathbf{u}_L \quad (2.3b)$$

$$\mathbf{s}_L = \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_L)(\overline{\mathbf{Y}_{LL}\mathbf{u}_L + \mathbf{Y}_{L0}u_0}) \quad (2.3c)$$

From equation (2.3c), we can write:

$$\text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_L)^{-1} \mathbf{s}_L = \overline{\mathbf{Y}_{L0} \mathbf{u}_0} + \overline{\mathbf{Y}_{LL} \mathbf{u}_L}$$

$$-\overline{\mathbf{Y}_{L0} \mathbf{u}_0} + \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_L)^{-1} \mathbf{s}_L = \overline{\mathbf{Y}_{LL} \mathbf{u}_L}$$

$$-\overline{\mathbf{Y}_{L0} \mathbf{u}_0} + \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_L)^{-1} \mathbf{s}_L = \overline{\mathbf{Y}_{LL} \overline{\mathbf{u}_L}}$$

$$\overline{\mathbf{Y}_{LL} \overline{\mathbf{u}_L}} = -\overline{\mathbf{Y}_{L0} \mathbf{u}_0} + \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_L)^{-1} \mathbf{s}_L$$

$$\overline{\mathbf{Y}_{LL} \overline{\mathbf{u}_L}} = -\overline{\mathbf{Y}_{L0} \mathbf{u}_0} + \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_L)^{-1} \mathbf{s}_L$$

$$\mathbf{u}_L = -\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \mathbf{Y}_{L0} \mathbf{u}_0 + \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{u}_L})^{-1} \overline{\mathbf{s}_L}$$

$$\mathbf{u}_L = \mathbf{w} + \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{u}_L})^{-1} \overline{\mathbf{s}_L} \quad (2.4)$$

where ' \mathbf{w} ' is no load voltage i.e. $\mathbf{w} = -\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \mathbf{Y}_{L0} \mathbf{u}_0$

2.3 Solution of Load flow Problem

In this section, the solution of load flow problem will be described . After wards conditions for **existence** and **uniqueness** of solution will be given :

Power flow solution [8]

Given voltage at slack bus and power injections at all PQ Buses, i.e. (u_0, \mathbf{s}_L) , We can solve for voltages (\mathbf{u}_L) at all PQ buses by iterating equation (2.4) until convergence tolerance is reached, i.e

$$\mathbf{u}_L^{(k+1)} = \mathbf{w} + \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{u}_L^{(k)}})^{-1} \overline{\mathbf{s}_L} \quad (2.5)$$

until

$$\mathbf{u}_L^{(k)} - \mathbf{u}_L^{(k+1)} < \text{Tolerance Value}$$

Conditions for Existence and Uniqueness of Power flow solution [8]

Suppose we have no load voltage: $\mathbf{w} := -\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1}\mathbf{Y}_{L0}\mathbf{u}_0$ and current power injections at all PQ Buses i.e. $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_L$,

Define:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{W} &:= \text{diag}(\mathbf{w}) \\ \xi(\mathbf{s}_L) &:= \|\mathbf{W}^{-1}\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1}\mathbf{W}^{-1}\text{diag}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}_L)\|_\infty \\ \|\mathbf{A}\|_\infty &:= \max_i \sum_j |A_{ij}| \\ u_{min} &:= \max_j \left| \frac{(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L)_j}{\mathbf{w}_j} \right|\end{aligned}$$

Theorem: Let we have a solution for voltages at a given power injection (i.e. a $(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L, \hat{\mathbf{s}}_L)$ pair) at all PQ buses.

Now consider, we have another point \mathbf{s}_L , then if this point satisfies following conditions:

$$1. \quad \xi(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_L) < u_{min}^2 \quad (2.6)$$

$$2. \quad \Delta = \left(u_{min} - \frac{\xi(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_L)}{u_{min}} \right)^2 - 4\xi(\mathbf{s}_L - \hat{\mathbf{s}}_L) > 0 \quad (2.7)$$

then it can be stated that solution for voltages at this new point will '**exist**' and will be '**unique**'.

Moreover, the solution for voltages will belongs to D i.e. $\mathbf{u}_L \in D$ where:

$$\begin{aligned}D &:= \{ \mathbf{u}_L : |\mathbf{u}_{L_j} - \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{L_j}| \leq \rho |\mathbf{w}_j|, j = 1, \dots, n \} \quad \text{with} \\ \rho &:= \frac{\left(u_{min} - \frac{\xi(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_L)}{u_{min}} \right) - \sqrt{\Delta}}{2}\end{aligned}$$

2.4 Existence of Power Flow Solution

Figure 2.2: Figure shows the power flow manifold constructed for 3 bus power system with relatively high impedance values. This manifold shows how the voltage at "bus 1" changes when the real and reactive power injections at "bus 2" changes. It can be observed that Newton Raphson method did not converged when either the real or reactive power injections become too low.

Power flow problem is a nonlinear problem. There are various methods of solving a power flow problem. The most common of them are 'Newton Raphson' and 'fast decoupled load flow'. These methods work really well for transmission system problem where the system is of a meshed nature and have low impedances. But the convergence of these methods is not always guaranteed for distribution system network which is more of a radial nature and have high impedances. 'Fixed point method' is recently introduced for the solution of power flow problem for distribution grids. First chapter already provided the necessary conditions for the existence of solution of power flow problem using fixed point method. The figure 2.2 shows the power flow manifold for 3 bus power system introduced in chapter 1. The smooth part of the curve depicts the convergence of the Newton Raphson method for power flow solution while the rough and uneven part shows the non-convergence.

While solving OPF problem using linear programming method, we aim to iteratively move along the similar manifold. This iterative movement should have an appropriate step size in the steepest decreasing direction of the objective function. The term "appropriate" means that the step size should not be big enough that it lands in non-converging part of the manifold.

For deciding the step size to convergent region we will include (2.7) as a constraint while solving OPF. The term "Feasibility constraint" will be used for this constraint. Although (2.6) is also required to guarantee the existence of solution, but practically (2.7) is found to be enough even in the case when (2.6) is not satisfied. Moreover, in worst case, if we are unable to find any solution then the algorithm will reject the result of that particular iteration and decrease the allowed step size. The result of any particular iteration is also rejected and step size is decreased when any constraint is breached or the value of objective function increases. Step size is reduced by multiplying the second term in equation (2.7) with 2. The flowchart of the algorithm for optimizing the cost of operation using above mentioned technique

is presented in section 3.2 . In the next section, the 3 bus power system test case is introduced, which will be optimized in the further sections.

2.5 Linear Models for Balanced Power System

This section will analyze the use of “global linearization method” for linearizing non-convex power flow equations. The term “global” means that we will not rely on "Taylor series" based linearization technique. Rather we will use "slope-intercept form" for linearizing the power flow equations.

In Taylor series based linearization, the first order approximation of the original function is used to get “tangent” at the given operating point.

In slope-intercept form, we need zero (no load) point, current operating point and the slope between these two points for linearizing a function. The equation in a 2D x-y plane can be written as shown in equation (2.8). The first point will always be no load point i.e. the point at which power injections/consumption on PQ buses are zero (i.e. $sL=0$). Although it may not lie on the original manifold, it is predicted to provide the best possible approximation of the original manifold. The second point will be the current operating point (at which the function is to be linearized).

The following figure shows the difference between the Taylor series based (blue) and slope intercept based (red) linearization.

Figure 2.3: Figure shows power flow manifold (in black color) for 2 bus power system. Manifold depicts the change in voltage at second bus w.r.t change in real and reactive power generation at the same bus. First bus is considered as slack bus for this system. Local and global linearization is shown in blue and red colour respectively. Linearization of the original manifold is done at points of real power generation of -0.3 and reactive power generation of -0.95 at second bus.

$$y = mx + y_0 \quad (2.8)$$

where

- y : value of linearized function at any point 'x'
- x : any specified point
- m : slope of line
- y_0 : value of function when x attains a value of '0'

The main difficulty in deriving the global linearized approximation lies in finding an appropriate mathematical relation which can help us to find the slope for the global linearized approximation. Before the linearizations are done for balanced power system, some techniques for dealing with complex variables and complex functions are presented.

2.5.1 Some Techniques for Complex Differential Mathematics

In this section, some of the mathematical techniques used for linearizing power system equations are presented.

Techniques for Differentiating COMPLEX Valued Functions in REAL Domain

As we know that power system equations are developed in complex domain. But since optimization problem is solved in real domain, we have to decompose those equations into real domain. Suppose given a function :

$$f(x) = ay(x) \quad \text{where } f(x) \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times 1} ; a \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n} ; y(x) \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times 1} \quad (2.9)$$

define:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle a \rangle &= \begin{bmatrix} Re(a) & -Im(a) \\ Im(a) & Re(a) \end{bmatrix} ; N = \begin{bmatrix} I_{n \times n} & 0_{n \times n} \\ 0_{n \times n} & -I_{n \times n} \end{bmatrix} \\ I &:= \text{Identity Matrix} ; n := \text{Number of rows in } f(x) \end{aligned}$$

then the function 2.9 can be broken into real and imaginary parts and differentiated as:

$$\frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} Re(f(x)) \\ Im(f(x)) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} Re(x) \\ Im(x) \end{bmatrix}} = \langle a \rangle \times \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} Re(y(x)) \\ Im(y(x)) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} Re(x) \\ Im(x) \end{bmatrix}}$$

Now suppose the function 2.9 includes the conjugate of $y(x)$, then:

$$f(x) = a\overline{y(x)} \quad \text{where } f(x) \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times 1} ; a \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n} ; y(x) \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times 1} \quad (2.10)$$

Then the function 2.10 can be broken into real and imaginary parts and differentiated as:

$$\frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} Re(f(x)) \\ Im(f(x)) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} Re(x) \\ Im(x) \end{bmatrix}} = \langle a \rangle \times N \times \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} Re(y(x)) \\ Im(y(x)) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} Re(x) \\ Im(x) \end{bmatrix}}$$

Techniques for Differentiating Real and Imaginary Parts w.r.t Magnitude and Angle

Suppose we have a complex valued variable:

$$u = ze^{j\theta} = z\cos(\theta) + jsin(\theta) \quad (2.11)$$

then differential of real and imaginary part of 2.11 w.r.t its magnitude and angle can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} Re(u) \\ Im(u) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \theta \end{bmatrix}} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & -z\sin(\theta) \\ \sin(\theta) & z\cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix}$$

2.5.2 Derivation of global linearized equation

Sensitivity for Voltage Magnitude

The derivation is based on solution of power flow problem using fixed point method. The structure of fixed point based power flow equation provide an easy way of deriving equation for global linearization.

Consider equation (2.5). And consider a situation when we have a feasible operating point \hat{u}_L and \hat{s}_L . Then \hat{u}_L and \hat{s}_L is the solution of equation (2.5).

Now consider that the power injection changes. So with the change in power injections, the fixed point method will take a step from current operating point to update the value of voltages at new value of s_L . Since the fixed point equation for power flow solution take steps in linearized direction for any new value of s_L and this, so the slope of that linearized step can be found as follow.

Re-writing equation (2.5):

$$\mathbf{u}_L = \mathbf{w} + \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\hat{u}_L)^{-1} \bar{s}_L \quad (2.12)$$

Let p_L and q_L be the real and reactive powers respectively, then s_L can be written as:

$$\bar{s}_L = p_L - jq_L \quad (2.13)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_L}{\partial p_L} &= \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\hat{u}_L)^{-1} \\ \mathbf{M}_{\mathbf{u}_L(p_L)} &= \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\hat{u}_L)^{-1} \end{aligned} \right| \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_L}{\partial q_L} &= -j\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\hat{u}_L)^{-1} \\ \mathbf{M}_{\mathbf{u}_L(q_L)} &= -j\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\hat{u}_L)^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (2.14) \quad (2.15)$$

Equations (2.14) and (2.15) show the value for change in voltages with respect to change in real and reactive power respectively. As in distribution grid we are only interested in voltage magnitudes, and moreover we cannot deal with "complex

numbers" directly in an optimization problem so we have to reduce above equations in term of "real numbers". Above equations can be further reduced by using following partial derivative rule for getting sensitivity of voltage magnitude :

$$\frac{\partial |f(x)|}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{|f(x)|} \text{Re} \left(\overline{f(x)} \frac{\partial f(x)}{\partial x} \right)$$

$$\mathbf{Mv}_{\mathbf{L}(\mathbf{pL})} = \mathbf{diag}(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\mathbf{L}})^{-1} \text{Re} \left(\mathbf{diag}(\overline{\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{L}}}) \mathbf{Mv}_{\mathbf{L}(\mathbf{pL})} \right) \quad (2.16)$$

$$\mathbf{Mv}_{\mathbf{L}(\mathbf{qL})} = \mathbf{diag}(\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{\mathbf{L}})^{-1} \text{Re} \left(\mathbf{diag}(\overline{\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{L}}}) \mathbf{Mv}_{\mathbf{L}(\mathbf{qL})} \right) \quad (2.17)$$

So the global linearized equation for voltage magnitude can be written as:

$$\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{L}(\text{lin})} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Mv}_{\mathbf{L}(\mathbf{pL})} & \mathbf{Mv}_{\mathbf{L}(\mathbf{qL})} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{pL} \\ \mathbf{qL} \end{bmatrix} + |\mathbf{w}| \quad (2.18)$$

Sensitivity for Slack Bus Power

From (2.2) we can write the mathematical relation between slack bus power and the voltages across the system as:

$$s_0 = u_0 (\overline{\mathbf{Y}_{00}} u_0 + \overline{\mathbf{Y}_{0\mathbf{L}}} \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{L}})$$

Here,

$$s_0 = p_0 + jq_0 \quad (2.19)$$

So, the differential of real and imaginary parts of the equation can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} p_0 \\ q_0 \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{pL} \\ \mathbf{qL} \end{bmatrix}} = \langle u_0 \overline{\mathbf{Y}_{0\mathbf{L}}} \rangle \mathbf{N} \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{L}}) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{L}}) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{pL} \\ \mathbf{qL} \end{bmatrix}} \quad (2.20)$$

From equation (2.12) , we can get

$$\frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{L}}) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{L}}) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{pL} \\ \mathbf{qL} \end{bmatrix}} = \langle \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{LL}}^{-1} \mathbf{diag}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{L}})^{-1} \rangle \mathbf{N} \quad (2.21)$$

So by putting value of (2.21) into (2.20), we get:

$$\mathbf{Ms}_{0(\mathbf{sL})} = \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} p_0 \\ q_0 \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{pL} \\ \mathbf{qL} \end{bmatrix}} = \langle u_0 \overline{\mathbf{Y}_{0\mathbf{L}}} \rangle \mathbf{N} \langle \mathbf{Y}_{\mathbf{LL}}^{-1} \mathbf{diag}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbf{L}})^{-1} \rangle \mathbf{N} \quad (2.22)$$

So the global linearized equation for the slack bus power can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p0}_{Lin} \\ \mathbf{q0}_{Lin} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{M} \mathbf{s0}_{(s_L)} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{pL} \\ \mathbf{qL} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.23)$$

Line flows

Consider again the three bus power system described in chapter 2. The power flow "FROM" the first two buses can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} s_0^f &= u_0 \overline{i_{01}} & ; & & s_1^f &= u_1 \overline{i_{12}} \\ s_0^f &= u_0 (\overline{Y_{sh,0} u_0 + Y_{01} (u_0 - u_1)}) & ; & & s_1^f &= u_1 (\overline{Y_{sh,1} u_1 + Y_{12} (u_1 - u_2)}) \end{aligned}$$

based on above equations, the following new matrices are defined:

$$\mathbf{s}^f = \begin{bmatrix} s_0^f \\ s_1^f \end{bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{Y}^f = \begin{bmatrix} Y_{sh,01} + Y_{01} & -Y_{01} & 0 \\ 0 & Y_{sh,12} + Y_{12} & -Y_{12} \end{bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{A}^f = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

so, the generic form of power flowing from all the buses can be written as follows:

$$\mathbf{s}^f = \text{diag}(\mathbf{A}^f \mathbf{u}) \overline{\mathbf{Y}^f \mathbf{u}} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times 1} \quad (2.24)$$

where "m" is the total number of lines in the system.

A more generic form, separating pq buses from slack bus can be written as:

$$\mathbf{s}^f = \text{diag}(\mathbf{A}_0^f u_0 + \mathbf{A}_L^f \mathbf{u}_L) (\overline{\mathbf{Y}_0^f u_0 + \mathbf{Y}_L^f \mathbf{u}_L}) \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times 1} \quad (2.25)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}^f = [\mathbf{A}_0^f, \mathbf{A}_L^f] ; \quad \mathbf{Y}^f = [\mathbf{Y}_0^f, \mathbf{Y}_L^f]$$

In similar way, the power injected "TO" a bus $s^t = \begin{bmatrix} s_1^t \\ s_2^t \end{bmatrix}$ from other buses through a power line can be derived.

Losses

Based on intuition, we can say that the power which is injected from first bus and not received at the second bus can be termed as "power loss" in a certain line. So the equation for power losses in the whole network can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} s^l &= s_0^f + s_1^t + s_1^f + s_2^t \\ s^l &= \mathbf{u}^T \overline{\mathbf{Y} \mathbf{u}} \end{aligned}$$

A more generic form, separating pq buses from slack bus can be written as:

$$s^l = u_0 (\overline{Y_{00} u_0 + Y_{0L} \mathbf{u}_L}) + \mathbf{u}_L^T (\overline{Y_{L0} \mathbf{u}_0 + Y_{LL} \mathbf{u}_L}) \quad (2.26)$$

Sensitivities for complex voltage

Another representation for sensitivity for complex voltage will be derived in the following lines as was derived in section 2.5.2. This sensitivity matrix can be used for deriving further sensitivity matrix for power system operation

Rewriting equation 2.12:

$$\mathbf{u}_L = \mathbf{w} + \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L)^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{s}}_L \quad (2.27)$$

Using technique presented in 2.5.1 and taking differential of real and imaginary parts of voltage w.r.t real and imaginary parts of powers as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{M}_{\text{pLqL}}^{\mathbf{u}_L} &= \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{pL} \\ \text{qL} \end{bmatrix}} = \langle \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L)^{-1} \rangle_N \quad (2.28) \\ \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{vL} \\ \theta_L \end{bmatrix}} \times \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{vL} \\ \theta_L \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{pL} \\ \text{qL} \end{bmatrix}} &= \langle \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L)^{-1} \rangle_N \quad (2.29) \end{aligned}$$

where:

$$\mathbf{R} := \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{vL} \\ \theta_L \end{bmatrix}} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta & -\text{v}_L \cos\theta \\ \sin\theta & \text{v}_L \cos\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.30)$$

So,

$$\mathbf{M}_{\text{pLqL}}^{\text{vL}\theta_L} := \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{vL} \\ \theta_L \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{pL} \\ \text{qL} \end{bmatrix}} = \frac{1}{\mathbf{R}} \langle \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \text{diag}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L)^{-1} \rangle_N \quad (2.31)$$

Sensitivities for Line flows

In the method given below, the sensitivity of square of power flow from a bus is calculated (The main reason behind taking "square" is that the derivative of complex conjugate does not exist! and losses are directly proportional to the square of line flows). The power flow from a bus to another bus is equal to the line flow connecting the two buses. The limits on the line flows can be squared and added as a constraint.

$$|\mathbf{s}^f|^2 = \text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{s}^f})(\mathbf{s}^f) \quad (2.32)$$

$$\frac{\partial |\mathbf{s}^f|^2}{\partial \mathbf{s}_L} = \text{diag}(\text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f) - j\text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f)) \left(\frac{\partial(\text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f))}{\partial \mathbf{s}_L} + j \frac{\partial(\text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f))}{\partial \mathbf{s}_L} \right) \quad (2.33)$$

$$+ \text{diag}(\text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f) + j\text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f)) \left(\frac{\partial(\text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f))}{\partial \mathbf{s}_L} - j \frac{\partial(\text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f))}{\partial \mathbf{s}_L} \right) \quad (2.34)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= 2 \text{diag} \left(\text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f) \frac{\partial(\text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f))}{\partial \mathbf{s}_L} \right) + 2 \left(\text{diag}(\text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f)) \left(\frac{\partial(\text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f))}{\partial \mathbf{s}_L} \right) \right) \\ &= 2 \left[\text{diag}(\text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f)) \quad \text{diag}(\text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f)) \right] \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \mathbf{s}_L} \\ \mathbf{M}_{\text{plql}}^{|\mathbf{s}^f|^2} &:= \frac{\partial |\mathbf{s}^f|^2}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L \\ \mathbf{q}_L \end{bmatrix}} = 2 \left[\text{diag}(\text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f)) \quad \text{diag}(\text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f)) \right] \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L \\ \mathbf{q}_L \end{bmatrix}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.35)$$

as we can write :

$$\mathbf{M}_{\text{sf}}^{\mathbf{p}_L \mathbf{q}_L} := \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L \\ \mathbf{q}_L \end{bmatrix}} = \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L) \end{bmatrix}} \times \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L \\ \mathbf{q}_L \end{bmatrix}}$$

Rewriting equation 2.25:

$$\mathbf{s}^f = \text{diag}(\mathbf{A}_0^f u_0 + \mathbf{A}_L^f \mathbf{u}_L) \overline{(\mathbf{Y}_0^f u_0 + \mathbf{Y}_L^f \mathbf{u}_L)}$$

taking differential of real and imaginary parts of power "FROM" w.r.t real and imaginary parts of voltages as:

$$\mathbf{M}_{\text{plql}}^{\text{sf}} := \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L) \end{bmatrix}} = \quad (2.36)$$

$$\langle \text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{Y}_0^f u_0 + \mathbf{Y}_L^f \mathbf{u}_L}) \times \mathbf{A}_L^f \rangle + \langle \text{diag}(\mathbf{A}_0^f u_0 + \mathbf{A}_L^f \mathbf{u}_L) \rangle \times N \times \langle \mathbf{Y}_L^f \rangle \quad (2.37)$$

Putting value from equation 2.37 and 2.28 into 2.35:

$$\mathbf{M}_{\text{plql}}^{|\mathbf{s}^f|^2} := \frac{\partial |\mathbf{s}^f|^2}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L \\ \mathbf{q}_L \end{bmatrix}} = 2 \left[\text{diag}(\text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^f)) \quad \text{diag}(\text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^f)) \right] \times \mathbf{M}_{\text{plql}}^{\mathbf{s}^f} \times \mathbf{M}_{\text{plql}}^{\mathbf{u}_L} \quad (2.38)$$

So assuming zero line flows at no-load point, global linearized equation for line flows from all buses can be written as:

$$|\mathbf{s}^f|_{\text{Linearized}}^2 = \mathbf{M}_{\text{plql}}^{|\mathbf{s}^f|^2} \times \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L \\ \mathbf{q}_L \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.39)$$

Sensitivities for Losses

Taking differential of real and imaginary parts of Losses w.r.t real and imaginary parts of voltages as:

$$\mathbf{M}_{\text{pLqL}}^{\mathbf{s}^l} := \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^l) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^l) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L \\ \mathbf{q}_L \end{bmatrix}} = \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^l) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^l) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L) \end{bmatrix}} \times \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L \\ \mathbf{q}_L \end{bmatrix}}$$

The equation 2.26 for power losses is rewritten:

$$\mathbf{s}^l = u_0(\overline{\mathbf{Y}}_{00}\mathbf{u}_0 + \overline{\mathbf{Y}}_{0L}\mathbf{u}_L) + \mathbf{u}_L^T(\overline{\mathbf{Y}}_{L0}\overline{\mathbf{u}}_0 + \overline{\mathbf{Y}}_{LL}\overline{\mathbf{u}}_L)$$

taking differential of real and imaginary parts of power losses w.r.t real and imaginary parts of voltages as:

$$\mathbf{M}_{\mathbf{u}_L}^{\mathbf{s}^l} := \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{s}^l) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{s}^l) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L) \end{bmatrix}} = \langle u_0 \overline{\mathbf{Y}}_{0L} \rangle N + \langle (\overline{\mathbf{Y}}_{L0}\overline{\mathbf{u}}_0 + \overline{\mathbf{Y}}_{LL}\overline{\mathbf{u}}_L)^T \rangle + \langle u_L^T \overline{\mathbf{Y}}_{LL} \rangle N \quad (2.40)$$

Putting values from equation 2.28 and 2.40 into 2.40, we get

$$\mathbf{M}_{\text{pLqL}}^{\mathbf{s}^l} = \mathbf{M}_{\mathbf{u}_L}^{\mathbf{s}^l} \times \mathbf{M}_{\text{pLqL}}^{\mathbf{u}_L}$$

So assuming zero losses at no-load point, global linearized equation for total losses can be written as:

$$\mathbf{s}^l_{\text{Linearized}} = \mathbf{M}_{\text{pLqL}}^{\mathbf{s}^l} \times \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L \\ \mathbf{q}_L \end{bmatrix}$$

Chapter. 3

Optimal Power Flow For Balanced Power System

This chapter will describe the model, algorithm for the solution of OPF problem and its results for balanced power system.

3.1 Test Case

A test case is defined w.r.t the three bus example shown in chapter 2. This test case is shown in figure 3.1. Here, Bus '0' is slack bus. Bus '1' is a load bus having a real and reactive load of 1 per unit. Bus '2' is generator bus having variable generation. The objective here is to minimize the cost of generation where the cost per MWh is given in table 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Figure shows the power system model which is used for optimization of balanced power system

Parameter	Cost (D/MWh)
P_{0-gen}	9.5
Q_{0-gen}	2.4
P_{2-gen}	10
Q_{2-gen}	2.5

(a) Cost of Generations

Parameter	Value
Base MVA	1
Max./Min Capacities of P_{i-gen} and Q_{i-gen}	0/5 p.u.
Max./Min. allowed voltage	1.2/0.8 p.u.

(b) Miscellaneous values

Table 3.1: Data of figure 3.1

3.2 Algorithm

3.3 Results

For the analysis of results, a power flow manifold will be developed which will show how the voltage of load bus i.e. "Bus 1" will change with change in real and reactive power injection at "BUS 2" for each case. The movement of optimization point on that manifold will be shown.

For each case, the value of impedance connecting the adjacent buses will be changed and the process of optimization will be observed on power flow manifold. Comparison with the global minimum value obtained by Matpower [7] will also be done for each case.

3.3.1 Case 1

Initial operating point

Bus No.	P_{Load} (p.u.)	Q_{Load} p.u.	P_{gen} (p.u.)	Q_{gen} (p.u.)	Cost of P_{gen} (Dol/MWh)	Cost of Q_{gen} (Dol/MWh)	voltage magnitude
0	-	-	0.253	0.953	9.5	2.4	1.2
1	1	1	-	-	-	-	1.08
2	-	-	0.9	0.2	10	2.5	1.19
Total	1+1j		1.153+1.153j		14.191 Dol/MWh		-
Other Values							
Tolerance Value = 0.0012 , Line impedance = 0.12+0.12j							

Table 3.2: Initial operating point of figure ??

Optimized results

Figure 3.2: The manifold shows the path taken by optimization program

Bus No.	P_{Load} (p.u.)	Q_{Load} p.u.	P_{gen} (p.u.)	Q_{gen} (p.u.)	Cost of P_{gen} (Dol/MWh)	Cost of Q_{gen} (Dol/MWh)	voltage magnitude
0	-	-	0.56803	0.6964	9.5	2.4	1.2
1	1	1	-	-	-	-	1.07
2	-	-	0.5395	0.4111	10	2.5	1.17
Total	1+1j		1.1075+1.1075j		13.491 Dol/MWh		-
Other Values							
Number of iterations = 3, MATPOWER-Global Min cost = 13.42 (Dol/MWh)							

Table 3.3: Results of optimization for case 1

3.3.2 Case 2

Initial operating point

Bus No.	P_{Load} (p.u.)	Q_{Load} p.u.	P_{gen} (p.u.)	Q_{gen} (p.u.)	Cost of P_{gen} (Dol/MWh)	Cost of Q_{gen} (Dol/MWh)	voltage magnitude
0	-	-	0.3784	1.0784	9.5	2.4	1.2
1	1	1	-	-	-	-	0.9871
2	-	-	0.9	0.2	10	2.5	1.1528
Total	1+1j		1.2784+1.2784j		15.683 Dol/MWh		-
Other Values							
Tolerance Value = 0.0012 , Line impedance = 0.18+0.18j							

Table 3.4: Initial operating point of figure ??

Optimized results

Figure 3.3: The manifold shows the path taken by optimization program

Bus No.	P _{Load} (p.u.)	Q _{Load} p.u.	P _{gen} (p.u.)	Q _{gen} (p.u.)	Cost of P _{gen} (Dol/MWh)	Cost of Q _{gen} (Dol/MWh)	voltage magnitude
0	-	-	0.6930	0.6894	9.5	2.4	1.2
1	1	1	-	-	-	-	0.9926
2	-	-	0.4934	0.4970	10	2.5	1.1479
Total	1+1j		1.1864+1.1864j		14.415 Dol/MWh		-
Other Values							
Number of iterations = 24, MATPOWER-Global Min cost=14.29 (Dol/MWh)							

Table 3.5: Results of optimization for case 2

3.3.3 Case 3

Initial operating point

Bus No.	P _{Load} (p.u.)	Q _{Load} p.u.	P _{gen} (p.u.)	Q _{gen} (p.u.)	Cost of P _{gen} (Dol/MWh)	Cost of Q _{gen} (Dol/MWh)	voltage magnitude
0	-	-	0.5291	1.2291	9.5	2.4	1.2
1	1	1	-	-	-	-	0.8870
2	-	-	0.9	0.2	10	2.5	1.0965
Total	1+1j		1.4291+1.4291j		17.4763 Dol/MWh		-
Other Values							
Tolerance Value = 0.0012 , Line impedance = 0.22+0.22j							

Table 3.6: Initial operating point of figure ??

Optimized results

Figure 3.4: The manifold shows the path taken by optimization program

Bus No.	P _{Load} (p.u.)	Q _{Load} p.u.	P _{gen} (p.u.)	Q _{gen} (p.u.)	Cost of P _{gen} (Dol/MWh)	Cost of Q _{gen} (Dol/MWh)	voltage magnitude
0	-	-	0.6784	0.7529	9.5	2.4	1.2
1	1	1	-	-	-	-	0.9926
2	-	-	0.5766	0.5021	10	2.5	1.1479
Total	1+1j		1.255+1.255j		15.2737 Dol/MWh		-
Other Values							
Number of iterations = 221, MATPOWER-Global Min cost=15.03 (Dol/MWh)							

Table 3.7: Results of optimization for case 3

3.4 Discussion

The results shows a comparison of:

1. Minimized Cost with Matpower Global minimized cost.
2. Number of iterations done and step length.

The cost of Matpower is used as a bench mark for comparison of our results. Matpower provides the global minimum cost of operation. Since this is a small distribution system, the global minimum cost can be found. But for moderately large three phase unbalance distribution system, it is not a trivial task to calculate global minima. Moreover, till now no software or program exists which can provide global minimum cost for three phase unbalance system. Since our goal is to develop optimization program using similar algorithm for unbalance distribution system, we observe that the algorithm is working fairly well to provide local minima for balanced power system.

The step length and number of iterations are directly related to each other. The power flow manifold provide a clear visualization for the step size for each case. It can be observed that as the impedance of system increases, the step size is automatically adjusted (decreased).

The tolerance limit which is defined by user is used as the stopping criteria in our algorithm. It is not a trivial task to choose stopping criteria for a moderately large systems. A very small value for tolerance may result in huge number of iterations, while a big tolerance value can result in termination of program even before the local optimum is achieved. A new method for defining the optimum stopping criteria will be presented in chapter 6.

Chapter. 4

Multiphase Power System

This chapter will introduce the power system model for 3 phase power system which will be used in upcoming chapters as a base case for doing further analysis. Multiphase modelling is very well described in [9]. Interested readers can further check the quality of solutions using this method from the cited document.

4.1 Power System Model

Consider the figure 4.1 which shows 3 bus multiphase power network developed using pi model of a power distribution line. Here, Bus 0 is a slack bus while all other buses are PQ buses.

Figure 4.1: 3 Phase Power System Network

where

$Y_{[ft]}^{ph}$ = Matrix of Series admittance of line connection between bus f and bus t =

$$\begin{bmatrix} Y_{[ft]}^{aa} & Y_{[ft]}^{ab} & Y_{[ft]}^{ac} \\ Y_{[ft]}^{ba} & Y_{[ft]}^{bb} & Y_{[ft]}^{bc} \\ Y_{[ft]}^{ca} & Y_{[ft]}^{cb} & Y_{[ft]}^{cc} \end{bmatrix}$$

$Y_{[ft]}^{sh}$ = Matrix of Shunt admittance of line connection between bus f and bus t =

$$\frac{jw}{2} \begin{bmatrix} C_{[ft]}^{aa} & C_{[ft]}^{ab} & C_{[ft]}^{ac} \\ C_{[ft]}^{ba} & C_{[ft]}^{bb} & C_{[ft]}^{bc} \\ C_{[ft]}^{ca} & C_{[ft]}^{cb} & C_{[ft]}^{cc} \end{bmatrix}$$

The load or generation connected in Y or delta form at any bus can be represented as shown in figure 4.2 with arrows showing the direction of current flow:

Figure 4.2: Connections of Y and Delta type loads in 3 phase systems

For any bus 'j' we have following quantities for three phases i.e a,b and c: where

$$\text{Voltage at jth Bus} = \mathbf{u}_j := (u_j^a, u_j^b, u_j^c)^T$$

$$\text{Current injections from Y Loads/Generations} = \mathbf{i}_j^Y := (i_j^a, i_j^b, i_j^c)^T$$

$$\text{Powers injections from Y Loads/Generations} = \mathbf{s}_j^Y := (s_j^a, s_j^b, s_j^c)^T$$

$$\text{Current injections from Delta Loads/Generations} = \mathbf{i}_j^\Delta := (i_j^{ab}, i_j^{bc}, i_j^{ca})^T$$

$$\text{Powers injections from Delta Loads/Generations} = \mathbf{s}_j^\Delta := (s_j^{ab}, s_j^{bc}, s_j^{ca})^T$$

By using Kirchoff's voltage and current laws, we can relate them as:

$$\mathbf{s}_j^\Delta = \text{diag}(\Gamma \mathbf{u}_j) \overline{\mathbf{i}_j^\Delta}$$

$$\mathbf{s}_j^Y = \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_j) \overline{\mathbf{i}_j^Y} - \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_j) \Gamma^T \overline{\mathbf{i}_j^\Delta}$$

where :

$$\Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

4.2 Multi-phase Load-Flow Problem

Now we will introduce load flow problem for "1+n" Bus power system where first bus i.e. "0_{th} bus" will be slack bus and rest of "n" buses will be pq buses.

Let "L" indicates all pq buses in the system. Consider each nth pq bus have three phases. So the parameters for all pq buses can be combined into new parameters with L subscript having a dimension \mathbb{C}^{3n} . These new parameters can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_L^{abc} &:= (\mathbf{u}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{u}_n^T)^T \\ \mathbf{i}_L^Y &:= (\mathbf{i}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{i}_n^T)^T \\ \mathbf{i}_L^\Delta &:= (\mathbf{i}_1^\Delta, \dots, \mathbf{i}_n^\Delta)^T \\ \mathbf{s}_L^Y &:= ((\mathbf{s}_1^Y)^T, \dots, (\mathbf{s}_n^Y)^T)^T \\ \mathbf{s}_L^\Delta &:= ((\mathbf{s}_1^\Delta)^T, \dots, (\mathbf{s}_n^\Delta)^T)^T \end{aligned}$$

So the multi phase load flow problem is to satisfy following set of equations.

$$\text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_L^{abc}) \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{i}_L^\Delta + \mathbf{s}_L^Y = \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_L^{abc}) \mathbf{i}_L^Y \quad (4.1a)$$

$$\mathbf{s}_L^\Delta = \text{diag}(\mathbf{H} \mathbf{u}_L^{abc}) \mathbf{i}_L^\Delta \quad (4.1b)$$

$$\mathbf{i}_L^Y = \mathbf{Y}_{LO}^{abc} \mathbf{u}_0 + \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc} \mathbf{u}_L^{abc} \quad (4.1c)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{H} := \begin{bmatrix} \Gamma & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & \Gamma \end{bmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{Y}^{abc} := \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Y}_{00}^{abc} & \mathbf{Y}_{0L}^{abc} \\ \mathbf{Y}_{L0}^{abc} & \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{Voltage at slack bus} = \mathbf{u}_0 := (u_0^a, u_0^b, u_0^c)^T$$

$$\text{Bus Admittance matrix of the whole grid} = \mathbf{Y}^{abc} \in \mathbb{C}^{3(n+1) \times 3(n+1)}$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_{L0}^{abc} \in \mathbb{C}^{3n \times 3}$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_{0L}^{abc} \in \mathbb{C}^{3 \times 3n}$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_{00}^{abc} \in \mathbb{C}^{3 \times 3}$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_{00}^{abc} \in \mathbb{C}^{3n \times 3n}$$

4.3 Solution of Load flow Problem

In this section, the solution of load flow problem will be described. After wards conditions for **existence** and **uniqueness** of solution for three phase system will be given .

Power flow solution - Fixed Point Method [10]

Given voltage at slack bus and power injections at all PQ Buses, i.e. $(u_0, \mathbf{s}_L^Y, \mathbf{s}_L^\Delta)$, We can derive the following equation from equations (4.1) for voltages \mathbf{u}_L^{abc} at all pq buses:

$$\mathbf{u}_L^{abc} = \mathbf{w}^{abc} + \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc-1} \left(\text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{u}_L^{abc}})^{-1} \overline{\mathbf{s}_L^Y} + \mathbf{H}^T \text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{H} \mathbf{u}_L^{abc}})^{-1} \overline{\mathbf{s}_L^\Delta} \right) \quad (4.2)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{w}^{abc} := -\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc-1} \mathbf{Y}_{L0}^{abc} \mathbf{u}_0$$

if we iterate equation (4.2) for voltages at all pq buses, then the equation (4.2) for (k+1)th iteration can be written as:

$$\mathbf{u}_L^{abc(k+1)} = \mathbf{G} \left(\mathbf{u}_L^{abc(k)} \right) \quad (4.3)$$

So , we can solve for voltage at all pq buses given power injection at all nodes by iterating (4.3) until convergence criteria is met. i.e.

$$|\mathbf{u}_L^{abc(k)} - \mathbf{u}_L^{abc(k+1)}| < \text{Tolerance Value}$$

Conditions for Existence and Uniqueness of Power flow solution [10]

Lets define:

$$\mathbf{W} := \text{diag}(\mathbf{w})$$

$$\mathbf{L} := |\mathbf{H}| = \text{component-wise absolute value of matrix H}$$

$$\mathbf{s}_L := \left((\mathbf{s}_L^Y)^T, (\mathbf{s}_L^\Delta)^T \right) \in \mathbb{C}^{6N}$$

$$\xi^Y(\mathbf{s}_L) := \|\mathbf{W}^{-1} \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \mathbf{W}^{-1} \text{diag}(\mathbf{s}_L^Y)\|_\infty$$

$$\xi^\Delta(\mathbf{s}_L) := \|\mathbf{W}^{-1} \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{-1} \mathbf{H}^T \text{diag}(|\mathbf{L} \mathbf{w}^{abc}|)^{-1} \text{diag}(\mathbf{s}_L^\Delta)\|_\infty$$

$$\xi(\mathbf{s}_L) := \xi^Y(\mathbf{s}_L) + \xi^\Delta(\mathbf{s}_L)$$

and define following comparative quantities:

$$\alpha(\mathbf{u}_L) := \min_j \frac{|(\mathbf{u}_L)_j|}{|(\mathbf{w}^{abc})_j|}$$

$$\beta(\mathbf{u}_L) := \min_j \frac{|(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{u}_L)_j|}{(|\mathbf{L}\mathbf{w}^{abc}|)_j}$$

$$\gamma(\mathbf{u}_L) := \min \{ \alpha(u), \beta(u) \}$$

Theorem: Let we have a solution for voltages at given power injection (i.e. a $(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L, \hat{\mathbf{s}}_L)$ pair) at all PQ buses.

Now consider, we have another point \mathbf{s}_L , then if this point satisfies following conditions:

$$1. \quad \xi(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_L) < (\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L))^2 \quad (4.4)$$

$$2. \quad \xi(\mathbf{s}_L - \hat{\mathbf{s}}_L) < \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{(\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L))^2 - \xi(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_L)}{\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L)} \right)^2 \quad (4.5)$$

then it can be stated that solution for voltages at this new point will “**exist**” and will be “**unique**”.

Moreover, the solution for voltages will belongs to D i.e. $\mathbf{u}_L \in D$ where:

$$D := \left\{ \mathbf{u}_L : |\mathbf{u}_{L_j} - \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{L_j}| \leq \rho |(\mathbf{w}^{abc})_j|, j = 1, \dots, 3n \right\} \quad \text{with}$$

$$\rho := \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{(\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L))^2 - \xi(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_L)}{\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L)} \right) - \sqrt{\left(\frac{(\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L))^2 - \xi(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_L)}{\gamma(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_L)} \right)^2 - \xi(\mathbf{s}_L - \hat{\mathbf{s}}_L)}$$

The solution of load flow problem for small distribution system using fixed point method is compared with OPENDSS [11] in [9]. Interested readers are encouraged to read the cited publication.

4.4 Linear Models for Multiphase Power System

This section will derive the linearized equation similar to section 3 for multiphase system.

4.4.1 Sensitivity for Voltage Magnitudes w.r.t. Power injections

Following similar steps as done in section 3, the sensitivities of voltage magnitudes with respect to real and reactive powers will be derived. The equation for fixed point solution of power flow problem for multiphase power system can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{u}_L^{abc} = \mathbf{w}^{abc} + \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc-1} \left(\text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{u}}_L^{abc})^{-1} \overline{\mathbf{s}}_L^Y + \mathbf{H}^T \text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{H}\mathbf{u}}_L^{abc})^{-1} \overline{\mathbf{s}}_L^\Delta \right) \quad (4.6)$$

Let \mathbf{p}_L^Y and \mathbf{q}_L^Y be the real and reactive powers of "Y" type injections and \mathbf{p}_L^Δ and \mathbf{q}_L^Δ be the real and reactive powers of "Delta" type injections respectively,

then we can write:

$$\bar{s}_L^Y = \mathbf{p}_L^Y - j\mathbf{q}_L^Y \quad (4.7)$$

$$\bar{s}_L^\Delta = \mathbf{p}_L^\Delta - j\mathbf{q}_L^\Delta \quad (4.8)$$

Following similar procedure as that of section 3, we get:

$$\mathbf{M}_{u_L}^Y := \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_L^{abc}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_L^Y}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_L^{abc}}{\partial \mathbf{q}_L^Y} \right) = \left(\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc^{-1}} \text{diag}(\overline{\hat{u}_L^{abc}})^{-1}, -j\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc^{-1}} \text{diag}(\overline{\hat{u}_L^{abc}})^{-1} \right) \quad (4.9)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{u_L}^\Delta := \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_L^{abc}}{\partial \mathbf{p}_L^\Delta}, \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_L^{abc}}{\partial \mathbf{q}_L^\Delta} \right) = \left(\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc^{-1}} \mathbf{H}^T \text{diag}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{u}_L^{abc})^{-1}, -j\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc^{-1}} \mathbf{H}^T \text{diag}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{u}_L^{abc})^{-1} \right) \quad (4.10)$$

So, for getting sensitivity for voltage magnitude, we will use the formula:

$$\frac{\partial |f(x)|}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{|f(x)|} \text{Re} \left(\overline{f(x)} \frac{\partial f(x)}{\partial x} \right)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{v_L}^Y := \text{diag}(\hat{v}_L^{abc})^{-1} \text{Re} \left(\text{diag}(\overline{\hat{u}_L^{abc}}) (\mathbf{M}_{u_L}^Y) \right) \quad (4.11)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{v_L}^\Delta := \text{diag}(\hat{v}_L^{abc})^{-1} \text{Re} \left(\text{diag}(\overline{\hat{u}_L^{abc}}) (\mathbf{M}_{u_L}^\Delta) \right) \quad (4.12)$$

So the global linearized equation for voltage magnitude can be written as:

$$\mathbf{v}_{L_{lin}}^{abc} = \mathbf{M}_{v_L}^Y \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L^Y \\ \mathbf{q}_L^Y \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{M}_{v_L}^\Delta \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L^\Delta \\ \mathbf{q}_L^\Delta \end{bmatrix} + |\mathbf{w}^{abc}| \quad (4.13)$$

4.4.2 Sensitivity for Slack Bus Power w.r.t. power injections

Using similar idea of equation (2.2), we can write the mathematical relation between slack bus power and the voltages across the system as:

$$\mathbf{s}_0^{abc} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_0) (\overline{\mathbf{Y}_{00}^{abc}} \mathbf{u}_0 + \mathbf{Y}_{0L}^{abc} \mathbf{u}_L^{abc}) \quad (4.14)$$

Here,

$$\text{Power injections at slack bus} := \mathbf{s}_0^{abc} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{s}_0^a \\ \mathbf{s}_0^b \\ \mathbf{s}_0^c \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{p}_0^{abc} + j\mathbf{q}_0^{abc} = \begin{bmatrix} p_0^a + jq_0^a \\ p_0^b + jq_0^b \\ p_0^c + jq_0^c \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.15)$$

So, the differential of real and imaginary parts of the equation can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_0^{abc} \\ \mathbf{q}_0^{abc} \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L \\ \mathbf{q}_L \end{bmatrix}} = \square (\text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_0) \overline{\mathbf{Y}_{0L}^{abc}}) \square \left(\frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L^{abc}) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L^{abc}) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L^Y \\ \mathbf{q}_L^Y \end{bmatrix}} + \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L^{abc}) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L^{abc}) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L^\Delta \\ \mathbf{q}_L^\Delta \end{bmatrix}} \right) \quad (4.16)$$

where:

$$\square(\cdot)\square = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\cdot) & \text{Im}(\cdot) \\ \text{Im}(\cdot) & -\text{Re}(\cdot) \end{bmatrix}$$

Rewriting (4.6) ,

$$\mathbf{u}_L^{abc} = \mathbf{w}^{abc} + \mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc-1} \left(\text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{u}_L^{abc}})^{-1} \overline{\mathbf{s}_L^Y} + \mathbf{H}^T \text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{H}\mathbf{u}_L^{abc}})^{-1} \overline{\mathbf{s}_L^\Delta} \right) \quad (4.17)$$

We can differentiate real and imaginary part of voltages with respect to real and imaginary "Y" and "Delta" powers as:

$$\alpha = \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L^Y \\ \mathbf{q}_L^Y \end{bmatrix}} = \square(\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc-1} \text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{u}_L^{abc}})^{-1})\square \quad (4.18a)$$

$$\beta = \frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}(\mathbf{u}_L) \\ \text{Im}(\mathbf{u}_L) \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L^\Delta \\ \mathbf{q}_L^\Delta \end{bmatrix}} = \square(\mathbf{Y}_{LL}^{abc-1} \mathbf{H}^T \text{diag}(\overline{\mathbf{H}\mathbf{u}_L^{abc}})^{-1})\square \quad (4.18b)$$

Equation (4.19) can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_{0Lin}^{abc} \\ \mathbf{q}_{0Lin}^{abc} \end{bmatrix}}{\partial \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L \\ \mathbf{q}_L \end{bmatrix}} = \square(\text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_0) \overline{\mathbf{Y}_{0L}^{abc}})\square (\alpha + \beta) \quad (4.19)$$

So the global linearized equation for the slack bus power can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_{0Lin}^{abc} \\ \mathbf{q}_{0Lin}^{abc} \end{bmatrix} = \square(\text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_0) \overline{\mathbf{Y}_{0L}^{abc}})\square \left(\alpha \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L^Y \\ \mathbf{q}_L^Y \end{bmatrix} + \beta \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_L^\Delta \\ \mathbf{q}_L^\Delta \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (4.20)$$

Chapter. 5

Optimal Power Flow For Multiphase Power System

In this chapter, a multiphase power system test case will be introduced in the first section. In the second section, the operation of the multiphase power system will be optimized using the similar algorithm which was introduced in chapter 3. In the third section, another algorithm for solving OPF called "Trust Region" will be introduced and its results will be compared.

5.1 Test Case

In this section, a test case for multiphase OPF is developed by extending IEEE 4 bus power distribution system to 6 bus power system so that more loads and generators can be accommodated. Figure of extended power system is shown in figure 5.1 and operating data is given in Table 5.1. Here, "BUS 0" is the slack bus where as all other buses are PQ buses. Generators of "Y" and loads of "Y and Delta" types are introduced into the system at various nodes. Cost for real and imaginary powers are assigned to each generators. Initially, all generation is concentrated at slack bus. As it can be seen from the data of the system that slack bus is an expensive option as compared to other buses, so it can be predicted that optimization process will shift the generation to other buses.

Figure 5.1: 3 phase 6 Bus power system

Bus No.	Phase	voltage magnitude (kV)	Load		Generation		Cost (Dollars/MWh)	
			Type	Value (KW+jkVar)	Type	Value (KW+jkVar)	Real Power	Reactive Power
0	a	7.1996	-	-	Y	1333.9+j704.5	0.13	0.05
	b	7.1996	-	-	Y	712.3+j225.8	0.13	0.05
	c	7.1996	-	-	Y	629.2+j332.3	0.13	0.05
1	a	7.1335	-	-	Y	0	0.11	0.04
	b	7.2065	-	-	-	-	-	-
	c	7.1773	-	-	Y	0	0.12	0.03
2	a	2.3454	Y	600+j200	-	-	-	-
	b	2.3894	Y	500+j200	-	-	-	-
	c	2.3781	D (a-c)	300+j200	-	-	-	-
3	a	2.2536	-	-	Y	0	0.11	0.05
	b	2.4345	D (b-c)	300+j200	-	-	-	-
	c	2.2798	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	a	2.1720	Y	600+j200	-	-	-	-
	b	2.4948	-	-	Y	0	0.12	0.03
	c	2.2113	-	-	Y	0	0.11	0.03
5	a	2.2006	-	-	Y	0	0.12	0.02
	b	2.4844	-	-	Y	0	0.11	0.04
	c	2.1567	Y	300+j100	-	-	-	-
TOTAL			2600+j1100		2675.4+j1262.6		410.93	
Other Values								
Tolerance Value = 0.01								
Admittance of line connection between two Buses (simon/feet)=								
$\begin{bmatrix} 0.4576 + 1.078i & 0.1559 + 0.5017i & 0.1535 + 0.3849i \\ 0.1559 + 0.5017i & 0.4666 + 1.04828i & 0.158 + 0.4236i \\ 0.1535 + 0.3849i & 0.158 + 0.4236i & 0.4615 + 1.065i \end{bmatrix} / 5280$								

(a) Initial Operating point of figure 5.1

Buses	Distance(feet)
0-1	2000
2-3	2500
3-4	2500
4-5	2500

(b) Distance between buses

Parameter	value
Magnitude of Voltage at Slack bus	7.199 kV
Transformer Location	Bus1 and 2
Transformer turn ratio	2.997
Rated Primary side voltage of all buses	7.199 kV
Minimum allowed voltage on primary side buses	5.75 kV
Rated Secondary side voltage of all buses	2.401 kV
Minimum allowed voltage on secondary side buses	1.92 kV

(c) Miscellaneous Data

Table 5.1: Data of figure 5.1

5.2 Results

The same algorithm as introduced in chapter 3 is used to optimize the operation of multiphase power system. The optimized results are shown in figure 5.2 below. It can be seen that almost all of the generation is shifted from the slack bus to PQ buses, which have cheaper generation options. Moreover, it can also be seen that the voltages are well under limited range.

Bus No.	Phase	voltage magnitude (kV)	Load		Generation		Cost (Dollars/MWh)	
			Type	Value (KW+jkVar)	Type	Value (KW+jkVar)	Real Power	Reactive Power
0	a	7.1996	-	-	Y	0.22+j4.18	0.13	0.05
	b	7.1996	-	-	Y	121.39+j5.78	0.13	0.05
	c	7.1996	-	-	Y	1.11-j0.70	0.13	0.05
1	a	7.1965	-	-	Y	594.42+j163.23	0.11	0.04
	b	7.1959	-	-	-	-	-	-
	c	7.2031	-	-	Y	0.00+j0.00	0.12	0.03
2	a	2.3890	Y	600+j200	-	-	-	-
	b	2.3985	Y	500+j200	-	-	-	-
	c	2.4029	D (a-c)	300+j200	-	-	-	-
3	a	2.4384	-	-	Y	738.63+j0.00	0.11	0.05
	b	2.4686	D (b-c)	300+j200	-	-	-	-
	c	2.3819	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	a	2.4346	Y	600+j200	-	-	-	-
	b	2.6296	-	-	Y	0.00+j311.52	0.12	0.03
	c	2.3565	-	-	Y	597.77+j325.97	0.11	0.03
5	a	2.6092	-	-	Y	0.00+j515.66	0.12	0.02
	b	2.6663	-	-	Y	594.29+j0.00i	0.11	0.04
	c	2.2231	Y	300+j100	-	-	-	-
TOTAL				2600+j1100		2647.83+j1327.04	335.08	
Other Values								
Number of iterations = 9								

Table 5.2: Optimized operation of system shown in Figure 5.1

5.3 Trust Region Algorithm

This section describes another algorithm for solving OPF using linearization technique. The algorithm is named as "Trust Region Algorithm". It starts by taking a user defined step size in the decreasing direction of the objective function. Then it decreases/increases its step size depending on the quality of the new point found. The program stops when the predefined tolerance value becomes greater than the maximum of change in all control variables.

5.3.1 Algorithm

5.4 Results - Trust Region Algorithm

The same problem as shown in table 5.1 is optimized using trust region method by using different values of initial step size (= Delta) . A value of "Nu = 0.1" is used. The optimized results are shown below.

Case1

Parameter	Value
Initial Cost of generation	410.93 D/MWh
Manual Settings	
Delta	200 kW
Tolerance	0.01

(a) Initial Data for Trust Region

Results	
Parameter	Value
Optimized Cost of generation	336.25 D/MWh
No. of iterations	51

(b) Results

Table 5.3: Optimized result with delta = 200kW

Case2

Parameter	Value
Initial Cost of generation	410.93 D/MWh
Manual Settings	
Delta	150 kW
Tolerance	0.01

(a) Initial Data for Trust Region

Results	
Parameter	Value
Optimized Cost of generation	336.024 D/MWh
No. of iterations	35

(b) Voltage at buses

Table 5.4: Optimized result with delta = 150kW

Case3

Parameter	Value
Initial Cost of generation	410.93 D/MWh
Manual Settings	
Delta	100 kW
Tolerance	0.01

(a) Initial Data for Trust Region

Results	
Parameter	Value
Optimized Cost of generation	335.493 D/MWh
No. of iterations	42

(b) Voltage at buses

Table 5.5: Optimized result with delta = 100kW

Case4

Parameter	Value
Initial Cost of generation	410.93 D/MWh
Manual Settings	
Delta	50 kW
Tolerance	0.01

(a) Initial Data for Trust Region

Results	
Parameter	Value
Optimized Cost of generation	334.96 D/MWh
No. of iterations	45

(b) Voltage at buses

Table 5.6: Optimized result with delta = 50kW

5.5 Conclusions

It can be seen from section 5.2 and section 5.4 that the optimization results are composed of two main parts:

1. Optimized Cost of generation.
2. Number of iterations.

5.5.1 Optimized cost of generation

As we already know that OPF is a non-convex problem. A non-convex problem have more then one minima. Each of these minimas is termed as "local minima" and the lowest of all those local minimas is termed as "global minima". As it is already stated in section 3.4, that finding a global minima is not a trivial and till yet no software/program exists which can calculate the global minima for three phase unbalanced power system (as per writer's knowledge). So the aim here was to find local minima while making the optimization process more robust. For the results shown in section 5.4, the cost vs power injection curve is drawn. Since power injections are multidimensional which can not be shown in 2D or 3D curve, so x axis just depicts different values of power injections.

Figure 5.2: Figure shows existence of more then 1 minima for non-convex problem

It can be observed that in each case, optimization processes ended up at different local minima. So the performance of both algorithms **can not be compared and judged based on its final value** since **all of them ended up at one of the minima.**

5.5.2 Number of iterations and step size

Number of iterations and step size are highly related to each other. The difficulty of manual adjustment of step size is alleviated by using the existence and uniqueness condition. Since the "tolerance limit" and the system used in section 5.2 and section 5.4 are same **AND** the minima for both of them are not very spread out, so the comparison can be made between the results of these two systems. The quantitative comparison of number of iteration between them showed that "existence and uniqueness" condition helped to converge the OPF problem in less iteration. It took "9 iterations" while trust region algorithm took around "3.5 to 5 times" more iterations to converge to similar results. Hence it can be concluded that "existence and uniqueness" condition can help to better adjust the step size and thus converges OPF problem faster if the minima are not very spread out from each other. Hence, it can be concluded that by using the condition for existence of power flow solution, various objectives related to power systems operation and design can be optimized and suitable step size can be found for each iteration.

Chapter. 6

Algorithm Based On Optimum Stopping Criteria

This chapter describes another algorithm for the solution of optimal power flow problem using linearization technique.

The algorithm is named as "Solution Existence Algorithm". It uses similar condition for deciding the step size for each iteration as in chapter 3. This condition is described in equation 4.5. The difference in this algorithm as compared to one presented in chapter 3 is the stopping criteria. The tolerance limit which was previously used as stopping criteria may have very small or very large value. This may result in either huge number of iterations or termination of the program even before the local optimum is achieved. Thus, this limit may not provide feasible stopping tolerance value. The optimum "tolerance value" is also found using equation 4.5 for no-load power system. The logic behind finding the optimum tolerance value is described in the next section.

6.1 Optimum stopping criteria

The purposed optimum stopping criteria is calculated by first determining the "maximum change in loading" (i.e. step size) allowed while guaranteeing the "existence of solution" for the given unloaded power system. And then taking a certain percentage of that "allowed step size" as the tolerance limit. By unloaded power system, it is meant that there will be Y connected injections (load and generation) at all "PQ" buses and all these injections will have a value of "zero". The condition described in equation 4.5 will be used as a constraint for guaranteeing the "existence of solution".

The objective function which will be minimized for finding optimum stopping criteria will be the Real power injections on all PQ buses. And the percentage value of 0.001 percent will be used to determine the tolerance limit.

'Solution Existence Algorithm' is presented in next sections below:

6.2 Solution Existence Algorithm

6.3 Solution existence Algorithm - Results

6.3.1 Results - 1

The same system as described in table 5.1 is optimized using 'Solution Existence Algorithm'.

Parameter	Value
Initial Cost of generation	410.93 D/MWh

(a) Initial Data for Algorithm

Results	
Parameter	Value
Optimized Cost of generation	334.66 D/MWh
No. of iterations	18

(b) Voltage at buses

Table 6.1: Optimized results using solution existence algorithm

6.3.2 Results - 2

In this case, the impedance of the whole system is increased by the factor of 2 and the performance of the algorithms is checked .

Parameter	Value
Initial Cost of generation	432.708 D/MWh

(a) Initial Data for Trust Region

Results	
Parameter	Value
Optimized Cost of generation	360.25 D/MWh
No. of iterations	66

(b) Voltage at buses

Table 6.2: Optimized results using solution existence algorithm when system impedance is doubled

6.4 Conclusions

It can be seen from results, that solution existence algorithm produce almost similar results as previous algorithms. Hence, stopping criteria for iterative programs can also be found using condition for the existence of solution. Finding tolerance value using this technique can be useful when the power system is of big size and stopping tolerance can not be decided manually.

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